

TWINNED
By Stars

D3.2 CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS ON TOURISM PRODUCT(S) PROGRAMME

**WP3 GENERATION OF NEW SPACES FOR CO-CREATION
OF NEW PRODUCTS AND NEW NAUTICAL TOURISM
EXPERIENCES**

TWINNEDBYSTARS

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

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DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
TbS	TWINNEDbySTARS
D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
T	Task
ORs	Outermost regions
ADFMA	Associação para o Desenvolvimento e Formação do Mar dos Açores
OMA	Observatorio do Mar dos Azores

SUMMARY

Work package title: Generation of new spaces for co-creation of new products and new nautical tourism experiences

Task: 3.2 Design and implementation of the co-creation workshops on tourism products

Deliverable: Co-creation workshops on tourism product(s) programme

Amount of co-creation workshops: four workshops, one per region

Regions involved: the four outermost regions (ORs) of this project were involved (Martinique, Madeira, Canary Islands and Azores).

Co-creation workshops:

1. Canary Islands, 23-24th September 2024
2. Madeira, 23-24th October 2024
3. Martinique, 13-14th November 2024
4. Azores, 28th November 2024

Organisers: **ULPGC-TIDES** as responsible of task 3.2, **NAUTIC OCEAN** as WP3 leader, **Consulta Europa** for the communication tasks, and count with the support of all partners.

1. OBJECTIVES OF THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS

The co-creation workshops aimed to fostering collaboration among local entrepreneurs to facilitate innovative ideas. These workshops brought together participants from the Canary Islands, Madeira, Martinique, and the Azores to co-create joint business ideas with potential to become in regional tourism products and promote joint ventures.

As part of the project's strategy to "Generate spaces for the co-creation of new nautical tourism experiences through innovative, sustainable, and circular business models," the workshops focused on designing tourism products that leveraged the regions' unique attributes, such as marine ecosystems and biodiversity, starlight conditions, and traditional navigation routes. Additionally, they promoted sustainable practices to protect marine biodiversity and preserve local cultural heritage.

Besides, the workshops aimed to strengthen the existing network of tourism actors across the regions by fostering synergies, knowledge exchange, and joint ventures through the ideation phase and the work in the different thematic tables. By supporting the development of business plans throughout the four workshops, it is sought to drive economic growth, create jobs, and attract investment. Ultimately, the goal is to develop sustainable, innovative tourism products that enhance the regions' image as outstanding maritime and nautical destinations, contributing to their long-term visibility and economic prosperity.

An additional objective of the workshops was to progress in Task 2.1, "Co-design of the Training Programme" under Work Package 2, "Upskilling and Capacity Building." This

part of the workshops explored methods for making businesses more circular and sustainable, offering capacity-building opportunities. Participants also completed an online survey to individually identify their specific needs, helping to co-design tailored courses for them. These efforts aligned with Task 2.2, which focused on developing and implementing training and self-diagnostic tools to help SMEs identify innovation opportunities. Information on this part of the workshop will be given under deliverable 2.1 'Training programme methodology' and deliverable 2.2 'Report on the conclusions of the training'. Some outputs are listed on [annex](#), although a specific deliverable will be dedicated to it.

2. METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS

Twinned by Stars was designed around key pillars: **capacity building** and **open innovation & new product development**. All this supported by different engagement and communication plans, surveys and regional exchange and collaboration (*Figure 1*). The co-creation workshops were developed to address and integrate all these pillars effectively.

All the TbS community was invited, prioritising local stakeholders and SMEs of each region (see D1.1 and D1.2 for details about how the project partners built the TbS community). The four workshops were conducted in the **local language** to ensure accessibility and inclusivity for local businesses.

A small number of guest enterprises from other regions were invited to add value, sharing external perspectives and expertise, as the primary focus was on **regional exchange**. As the workshops progressed, the Twinned by Stars community grew stronger and more interconnected through synergies between the most committed stakeholders.

Figure 1. Project's main objectives.

The methodology was designed to create a cohesive and **interconnected series of regional workshops**, rather than four simultaneous and isolated events (*Figure 2*). The workshops were then developed with a **snowball effect**, beginning with the foundational step of "landing" ideas in the first workshop.

From the first workshop in Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, to the final one in Faial, Azores, the approach aimed to foster continuity and collaboration, ensuring that each session built upon the previous one. The initial ideas were thus formed and refined, setting the groundwork for the next phase, in which more ideas emerged, as new enterprises were joining.

- **Workshop 1:** The initial session focused on creating an inventory of business ideas, where participants brainstormed a wide range of possibilities.
- **Workshops 2-4:** These workshops were dedicated to refining and developing the ideas from Workshop 1. Participants “landed” the ideas by structuring them and working on actionable steps to build the product.

Figure 2. Workshop methodology.

As the workshops progressed, new enterprises were encouraged to join, either contributing to existing product ideas or introducing new concepts. This iterative process not only enriched the ideas but also strengthened the sense of community and collaboration among participants, creating a dynamic and evolving network.

One advantage of organising the workshops in a serial manner and not simultaneously is the possibility to manage and circulate a lot of qualitative information across the workshops.

In general, the co-creation workshops followed an ordered step process:

STEP 1. Inspiration - Empathise: Setting the context and fostering understanding.

STEP 2. Brainstorming: Generating innovative ideas collaboratively.

STEP 3. Landing Business Ideas: Refining concepts into actionable business proposals.

STEP 4. Building Consensus and Exchange: Aligning participants and encouraging knowledge sharing.

Typical materials and tools utilised across the 4 workshops were:

- Agenda of the meeting
- Video presentations of the project and the enterprises (STEP 1)

- Power point presentations of enterprises (best practices and inspirations talks) (STEP 1)
- Brainstorming game (word cloud) (STEP 2)
- Thematic tables (STEP 3)
- Posters -Tripple layered Business Model Canvas (STEP 3)
- Post-its (STEP 3)
- Round table (STEP 4)

3. STRUCTURE OF THE WORKSHOPS

The agendas for the 4 workshops were very similar. The first slot entailed welcoming words from the local partner, followed by a presentation of the project the purpose of the event. The project's community was introduced, and then the participating businesses and stakeholders. This was accompanied by conferences showcasing success stories that embraced innovation, sustainability, and circularity in tourism, leading to the ordered step process described above.

On average one full day (2 sessions) were dedicated to brainstorm product ideas, and a half day dedicated to WP3 (training needs) and the self-assessment tool. However, this structure was adapted to suit the specific needs of each workshop.

AGENDA / TALLER DE CO - CREACIÓN
Islas Canarias

23 y 24 de septiembre de 2024

www.twinnedbystars.eu

Día 1. 23 de septiembre de 2024

- 09.00h - 09.30h Bienvenida
- 09.30h - 10.00h Presentación del proyecto, orden del día, objetivos, resultados esperados de la reunión
Xavier Martínez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN
- 10.00h - 10.30h El potencial de los cielos oscuros para mejorar tu oferta náutica
Frank A. Rodríguez, ASTROEDUCA
- 10.30h - 11.00h PAUSA CAFÉ
- 11.00h - 11.45h Ronda de presentaciones y presentación de la comunidad PYMES de TWINNEDbySTARS en su conjunto (Canarias, Azores, Madeira y Martinica)
Xavier Martínez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN
Yen E. Lam González, ULPGC-TIDES
- 11.45h - 12.05h Posibilidades tecnológicas en el sector náutico
Izzat Sabbagh Rodríguez, XREALITY FACTORY
- 12.05h - 12.20h Pesca turismo, Turismo acuícola y Turismo pesquero y marítimo
Francisco García Lascarain, CAPITAN MARITIMO DE LAS PALMAS
- 12.20h - 12.30h Homogeneización y fomento de la certificación
Adelina de la Jara, CLUSTER MARITIMO DE CANARIAS
- 12.30h - 13.00h Fase de ideación
Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN
- 13.00h - 15.30h A L M U E R Z O
- 15.30h - 16.30h Mesas temáticas: Canary Islands - Madeira - Azores - Martinica
Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN
- 16.30h - 17.30h Presentaciones de las mesas, recapitulación y selección de ACUERDOS y RESPONSABILIDADES CONJUNTAS
Xavier Martínez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN
- 20.00h Actividad de Teambuilding

Día 2. 24 de septiembre de 2024

- 09.30h - 10.00h Estrategias ambientales para hacer tu negocio más circular
Máyle Tarnes Espinosa, ELITTORAL
- 10.00h - 10.30h Presentación de la encuesta individual online de autoevaluación
Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES
- 10.30h - 11.00h PAUSA CAFÉ
- 11.00h - 11.30h Discusión sobre los resultados de la encuesta individual en línea para la autoevaluación. Momento de reflexión
Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES
- 11.30h - 12.30h Identificación de necesidades y co-diseño de los cursos de formación
Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES

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Figure 3. Example of the agenda. In this case, Canary Islands workshop.

For instance, due to social unrest, the workshop in **Martinique** was adapted to an online format to ensure continuity which resulted in a positive outcome since more companies from all regions could participate. Additionally, the final workshop in the **Azores** included a consortium meeting prior to the training sessions. As a result, the planned two-day training was condensed into a single day. The morning was dedicated to WP3 dynamics and the afternoon to WP2 activities.

WP3 activities will be related in this deliverable whereas WP2 activities and results will be defined under D2.1 and D2.2 as explained above.

STEP 1 INSPIRATION – EMPATHISE

Its aim was to set the tone and inspire participants through concise, impactful "conference pills". These short presentations highlight **success stories, innovative best practices, or key insights** relevant to the workshop's objectives. The goal is to foster empathy and understanding of the shared challenges and opportunities faced by businesses in the context of ORs.

Figure 4. Representation of some of the inspiring talks.

The selected lectures were designed to showcase success stories, innovative practices and concrete examples of sustainability and circularity. These presentations aimed to motivate local businesses, offer practical ideas and set a collaborative tone from the start of the workshop. The list of inspiring lectures is presented below.

Table 1. List of inspirational conferences.

Workshop	Conference name	Enterprises speaker
Canary Islands	The potential of dark skies to enhance your nautical offering	ASTROEDUCA
	Technological possibilities in the nautical sector,	XRFactor
	Fisheries tourism, Aquaculture tourism and Fishing and seafood tourism,	MARINA de Gran Canaria
	Estrategias ambientales para hacer tu negocio más circular	ELITTORAL
Madeira	Ecological Approach to Dolphin and Whale Watching	MAGIC DOLPHIN
	VMT Madeira: A Sustainability Stakeholder	VMT MADEIRA
	Educação, ciência e interpretação a bordo	BIOSEAN
	Activities and objectives of the Madeira Astronomy Association	Madeira Astronomy Association

Martinique	ecoRoute sister project	University of the Antilles
	Sailing cargo ships: an innovative, ecological, economical and certified solution	SEAFRET
	Opportunités de vedettariat pour les entreprises de tourisme nautique.	NAUTIC OCEAN
	Gestion environnementale d'une marina	Le PORT du MARIN
	Sustainable maritime transport in the Caribbean	CANOPEE BLEUE
	New eco-tourism practices for sea excursions	Voile Nature
Azores	Sailing cargo ships: an innovative, ecological, economical and certified solution	SEAFRET
	Starlight charter opportunities for marine tourism companies.	NAUTIC OCEAN
	Ecological diving. Electrosolar diving support boat	CANOPEE BLEUE
	Entrepreneurship in the Blue Economy Advantages of an ecosystem model	ADFMA
	Bioacoustics as a tool for understanding, conservation and dissemination in nature tourism	BIOSEAN
	From ideas to action: Conservation Tourism	Naturalist Science & Tourism

On the [Annexes](#), links to all the presentations are given.

STEP 2 BRAINSTORMING

Following the inspiration phase, a brainstorming game session was held to identify the diverse interests and ideas of the participating companies. This slot was moderated by **ULPGC-TIDES** and **NAUTIC OCEAN**.

To facilitate this process, the software **Mentimeter** is used, allowing participants to anonymously contribute up to three ideas each in real-time. This approach ensures inclusivity, as all voices are represented.

Facilitators then guide the discussion to group similar ideas, identify recurring themes, and highlight key points for further exploration. The tool visually emphasized the most popular terms by enlarging them based on the number of mentions. During this phase, the participating enterprises worked to define their focus areas for the thematic tables. This process aimed to identify groups' key interests and categorise them into the most prominent topics. This exercise helped to clearly identify the distinct areas the enterprises were keen to explore, which then became the foundation for the next activity, "The Thematic Tables".

Canary Islands

Figure 5. Ideation phase for the Canary Islands Region

These concepts were group into four categories that defined 4 working groups/tables:

- 1) **Astronavigation.**
- 2) **Sustainability** as a business model.
- 3) **Education, Science and on-board interpretation.**
- 4) **Sea and Earth: themed products** (*volcanism, gastrotourism, culture and heritage*).

From these four, only the first and third were developed during the workshop.

Madeira

Figure 6. Ideation phase for Madeira.

In **Madeira** after the ideation phase the two tables that were developed in the past workshop continued. One of the tables that was not developed (table 4) was re-introduced and further developed by Madeiran enterprises:

- 1) **Astronavigation.**
- 2) **Ecotourism, hydrophones and sustainability.**
- 3) **Storytelling: themed routes** (*volcanism, gastrotourism, culture, heritage*)

By the end of this workshop, table 2 “ecotourism, hydrophones and sustainability” had driven away from the idea of hydrophones and data collection. Instead, they were focusing on an **Atlantic On-board internship programme**. Hence, in the Martinique workshop there was not 3 ideas but 4, accounting for table 2 dividing into ‘hydrophones and sounds’ and into the ‘internship programme’.

Martinique

Due to the social unrest situation in Martinique, the workshop was moved to online, and dynamics were slightly changed. Instead of an open ideation phase with a QR code registering everybody’s interest, the four ideas that had been born during the previous workshops were shared and participants were encouraged to add themselves to one of them or to create a new one. Furthermore, there was a great environmental and natural interest. The result was the following:

Quelle entreprise ou association représentez- vous	Quelle idée d'entreprise vous intéresse le plus ?
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	Atlantic Starlight Charter Experience (astrotourisme et navigat
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	Atlantic Starlight Charter Experience (astrotourisme et navigat
LA PIROGUE KALINA	Atlantic Starlight Charter Experience (astrotourisme et navigat
Cie seafret caraibes	Atlantic Starlight Charter Experience (astrotourisme et navigat
Cie Seafret Caraibes	On-board internships à la carte (accords internationaux et prog
ASSOCIATION TOTEM	On-board internships à la carte (accords internationaux et prog
LA PIROGUE KALINA	Storytelling : les routes des produits à thème Volcanisme, Gas
CTM	Storytelling : les routes des produits à thème Volcanisme, Gas
Dolphin and Whales s.l	Whale watching acoustic experience (hydrophones, stroytellin
Madeira boat rentals	Whale watching acoustic experience (hydrophones, stroytellin

Figure 7. Co-creation workshop ideation phase at Martinique.

In **Martinique**, the enterprises could join these four ideas and add new ones.

- 1) **Astronavigation**
- 2) **Hydrophones, whale sounds and data.**
- 3) **On board internships**
- 4) **Storytelling: themed routes (volcanism, gastrotourism, culture, heritage)**

There was interest in the four ideas, with enterprises not only from Martinique but also from Madeira and Canary Islands showing their interest in the ideas.

Using these tools, participants collaboratively outline the requirements, goals, and strategies needed to bring their ideas to life. The focus remains on practical implementation, considering the unique context and opportunities of each OR. Empty business model canvass can also be found in the [Annexes](#).

Figure 9. Business (red), environmental (green) and social (blue) model canvass.

In [Annexes](#) there is a section where you can see the three templates of the Business Model Canvas that were printed and utilised with post-its.

At this point, it is important to note that not all thematic tables became “products”. For instance, although the workshop in Canary Islands had four working tables, the business representatives ultimately decided to focus on just two of them. The other proposed working groups were still mentioned in the subsequent workshops, in case anyone wanted to revisit or revive those ideas. On the other hand, in Madeira, some entities participated in two tables, switching after the break as they were particularly interested in both ideas. This tailored grouping allowed for focused discussions, ensuring that the thematic tables reflected the specific priorities of the enterprises.

Here there is a summary of the business ideas that most progressed:

Idea 1. Atlantic Starlight Adventures.

[Here](#) you can see the progression from the workshops (the canvass scanned). Although at the end most of the work was done online.

[Here](#) you can see the online version of the 3-model canvass.

Idea 2. Atlantic on-board internship programme (& marine sounds)

Although at the end most of the work was done online, [here](#) you can see the progression from the workshops (the canvass scanned). This is specifically relevant for this idea that it was first focused on data sounds and then it transformed into the internship programme:

[Here](#) you can see the online version of the 3-model canvass.

Idea 3. Citizen Science

[Here](#) you can see the progression from the workshops (the canvass scanned).

[Here](#) you can see the online version of the 3-model canvass.

Idea 4. Storytelling

[Here](#) you can see the progression from the workshops (the canvass scanned):

[Here](#) you can see the online version of the 3-model canvass.

STEP 4 BUILDING CONSENSUS AND EXCHANGE

Presentation of tables, summary and selection of agreements and joint responsibilities

The final step focuses on consolidating the ideas developed in the previous phases and ensuring alignment across all participants. In this phase, representatives from each thematic table present their refined business ideas and solutions to the larger group. Each group shares their findings, key insights, and proposed strategies, providing an opportunity for feedback and further refinement.

To build consensus, the group engages in open discussion, where participants address any concerns, align their objectives, and make collective decisions on key aspects. Facilitators encourage dialogue to ensure that each company's vision is heard while fostering collaboration and mutual understanding.

Following these discussions, the group identifies specific agreements, responsibilities, and next steps to ensure that the ideas can be taken forward. This includes clarifying who will be responsible for what actions, how resources will be allocated, and how the progress of each initiative will be monitored.

In this section, the working groups showed their ideas and main work on their correspondent product. Here they were faced with questions by all the audience that helped fine tuning their canvasses.

It is worth mentioning that after each workshop there were calls and group meetings to keep working on their ideas and filling the canvas sections for the next workshop.

In the annex there is a list of the main [agreements](#) that were made to keep working on the ideas. Also, the annexes shows the [minutes](#) with a detailed information of these moments of debate, the [signature lists](#), and [photos](#) of each workshop.

BRINGING OTHER COMPANIES TO THE WORKSHOPS

As the workshops have progressed, we have been able to bring representatives from the most committed companies in other regions to participate. This approach ensures that each workshop benefits from a diverse representation of perspectives from across all four ORs, enriching the discussions and outcomes and pursuing our project's main goal which is to develop a multi-destination product.

As there are budgetary restrictions, project partners agreed on the criteria to invite SMEs from other regions. This was validated in a SC meeting. on three aspects. Three aspects were considered:

- Commitment to training and collaboration
- Commitment to sustainability
- Commitment to innovation

Table 2. SMEs invited to attend from a different Or than where the co-creation workshop was taking place.

WORKSHOP	SME	VALUE
Canary Islands	ADFMA (Escola do Mar)	Best practice as the Azores Sea School. Professional training center for maritime professions, developing new courses, supporting local institutions in educational policies, and fostering collaboration between public and private entities, while ensuring the implementation of management models and infrastructure to support maritime careers
	Biosean	Best practice on tourism and science, with monitorization of whales and other marine life. One of the few in his area (Tenerife).
	Happy Hour	Best practice on slow sailing and showing the intrinsic value of the sea.
Madeira	Biosean	Leader of the product “Internship programme”. Best practice on tourism and science, with an emphasis on marine sounds and customer experience.
	Naturalist	Best practice on Nature and Science, integrating university research with tourism, working with PhD and students to give back to nature as well as raising awareness and teaching about the sea.
Azores	Biosean	Leader of the product “Internship programme”. Best practice on tourism and science, with an emphasis on marine sounds and customer experience.
	Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	Best practice on slow tourism experience. Quite involved enterprise on the product “Atlantic Starlight Adventures”.
	Madeira Boat Rentals	Best practice on the union of various enterprises under a common standard.

	Seafret Caraibes	Best practice on the use of a solar sailing ship with a great interest to create synergies in the other ORs.
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3. RESULTS

As a result of the process four thematic products were collectively defined by enterprises from the four regions. These four products are summarised below.

ASTRONAVIGATION

Product name: **Atlantic Starlight Adventures**

Born: in the Canary Islands

Idea: Sales engine platform that offers night chartering to stargaze, combined with whales observing and learning about stars, astronomy, mythology...

Activities might include star-sailing; sunset star-sailing dinner experience; sunset star-sailing breakfast experience; 3-days experience sailing from the Canary Islands to Madeira, with stargazing over two nights, guided by an astronomer.

Companies involved

Canary Islands. Nautic Ocean, Keep Sailing, Biosean.

Martinique. La Pirogue Kalina, Seafret Caraibes.

Madeira. Happy Hour, Sunkiss Sailing, Madeira Boat Rentals.

Azores. Naturalist, Pure Adventure Azores.

Some key partners

Fundación Starlight (International), Associação de Turismo Sustentável do Faial (Azores), Marina do Funchal (Madeira), Astroeduca (Canary Islands), Associação de Astronomia da Madeira.

[Infographic](#)

Final state: fit for evaluation.

HYDROPHONES, WHALE SOUNDS AND DATA

Product name: **Whale Watching Acoustic Experience**

Born: in Canary Islands.

Idea: Hydrophones exploitation for on-board education, experiential value and storytelling: enterprises from madeira, Azores and Martinique incorporate a product innovation

Sub-product: Cetaceans Sounds Data. This is a product consisting of recorded sounds of sea and cetaceans, the exploitation of an encoded database with locations, time, species, day, season, and other surrounding characteristics of the sounds.

Companies involved:

Canary Islands. Biosean, Spirit of the Sea.

Madeira. VMT Madeira, Madeira Boat Rentals.

Azores. Naturalist.

Some Key partners:

Escola do mar dos Açores, Associação para o Desenvolvimento e Formação do Mar dos Açores and Canary on Board (podcast).

Final state: chosen for training instead of product development (see Figure 19, page 35).

ON BOARD INTERNSHIPS

Product name: **Atlantic On-board internships**

Born: in Madeira.

Idea: Certified internships in nautical enterprises located in Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands and Martinique. They consist of packages that include theoretical sessions, data collection, and hands-on training in multiple fields. Depending on the selected region, accommodation, airport transfers, duration of the internship and meals may or may not be included in the internship price. Each enterprise show their unique offer.

This is an opportunity to learn within a sea-focused culture, exploring marine biodiversity in the Atlantic, with a strong emphasis on social and environmental responsibility, which is a key value of the enterprises. These enterprises collaborate, sharing demand and resources to increase the scope of their actions and applied research.

The internships can be in one enterprise or region, or they can be shared with a cross-region circuit touching at least 2 islands.

Companies involved

Canary Islands. Nautic Ocean, Biosean.

Martinique. Seafret Caraibes, Totem.

Madeira. VMT Madeira, Sunkiss Sailing.

Azores. Naturalist, Sail Dive Azores, Dive Azores.

Some key partners

Canary On Board (communication), U4IMPACT or similar, scientific tourism travel agencies, universities, and other training programs that require students' internships, local tourist companies as they offer complementary experiences (land excursion, can be included in each internship program by paying a fee).

Infographic

Final state: fit for evaluation.

STORYTELLING: THEMED ROUTES

Product name: **Historical and cultural heritage-focused thematic journeys, including star gazing and regional stories.**

Born: in Madeira.

Idea: Daytime activities include coastal and scenic tours exploring geology and volcanic formations, along with experiential fishing heritage tours led by local fishermen, featuring artisanal fishing stories, supported by key resources such as fishermen, historians, associations (e.g., ACIF), and synergies with local businesses, while the main activities focus on storytelling-centered fishing heritage tours, complemented by merchandising materials that support the heritage and cultural narrative.

Companies involved

Madeira. ACIF, Diogo Nóbrega, la Maison ZiaZen, Ocean Devotion Madeira.

Martinique. Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique, la Pirogue Kalina.

Final state: It was not completed by the companies, so it was finally disregarded.

CITIZEN SCIENCE

Product name: **Citizen Science and Slow Tourism.**

Born: in Azores.

Idea: This product idea focuses on offering a year-long training program for young people seeking a gap year before college or university, with a value proposition that includes education and literacy, knowledge transmission, exhaustive data collection to support goals, a playful component, curriculum enhancement, soft skills development, and certifications accrediting the training.

Companies involved

Azores. EMA, OMA, Naturalist, Sail Azores Yacht Charter, Norberto Diver.

Some key partners

Academia, Mt enterprises, EMA, OMA, transport, KITS C.S companies, accommodation, restaurants.

Final state: It was not completed by the companies, so it was finally disregarded.

Only two products, named as **Atlantic Starlight Adventures and Atlantic On-board internships** reached the format and level of detail necessary to move to the anonymous voting system.

4. TECHNICAL DATA SHEET

Workshop number/title:	1
Location:	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Dates:	23 rd & 24 th September 2024
Type of event:	On-site
Language of event:.....	Spanish
Speakers (different from partners)	4 (Table 1)
Participants (total):	32, page 28
Participants (SMEs):.....	9, page 28
Agenda:	Figure 12
Presentations:	page 24
Minutes	page 24
Signature sheet:	page 29
Pictures of the event:	page 24

Workshop number/title:	2
Location:	Madeira
Dates:	23 rd & 24 th October 2024
Type of event:	On-site
Language of event:.....	Portuguese
Speakers (different from partners)	4 (Table 1)
Participants (total):	32, page 28
Participants (SMEs):.....	10, page 28
Agenda:	Figure 13
Presentations:	page 24
Minutes:	page 24
Signature sheet:	page 29
Pictures of the event:	page 24

Workshop number/ title:	3
Location:	Martinique
Dates:	13 & 14 November 2024
Type of event:	On-site
Language of event:.....	French, Spanish and Portuguese
Interpreters:.....	French, Spanish and Portuguese
Speakers (different from partners)	5 (Table 1)
Participants (total):	40, page 28
Participants (SMEs):.....	16, page 28
Agenda:	Figure 14
Presentations:	page 24
Minutes:	page 24
Signature sheet:	page 29
Pictures of the event:	page 24

Workshop number/title:	4
Location:	Faial Island, Azores
Dates:	28 th November 2024
Type of event:	On-site
Language of event:.....	Portuguese-English
Speakers (different from partners)	5 (Table 1)
Participants (total):	39, page 28
Participants (SMEs):.....	16, page 28
Agenda:	Figure 15
Presentations:	page 24
Minutes.	page 24
Signature sheet:	page 29
Pictures of the event:	page 24

5. EVALUATION OF THE PRODUCTS AND NEXT STEPS

Budget restrictions have led to define a voting system, in which partners and the rest of stakeholders decide, by majority, which product shows greater innovation and sustainability potential. To support the evaluation process, infographics were designed based on the information provided by the model canvases.

1. [Atlantic Starlight Adventures.](#)
2. [Atlantic On-board internships.](#)

These infographics were then shared with all project partners and stakeholders for a voting process through an [online questionnaire](#).

Results of the survey.

At the moment of submitting this deliverable ten responses had been received, mainly from the Canary Islands partners and stakeholders. A great variety of stakeholders will respond to the survey, which will be active during January 2025 collecting more responses.

Figure 10. Percentage of participation per region.

Figure 11. Percentage of participation per type of stakeholder.

The following table presents the average scores by aspect. Results show a clear preference and more positive evaluation for Product 1. Nevertheless, the final decision will be made during the SC meeting in January once we have collected more responses.

Aspects	Product 1. Astro navigation	Product 2. On-board internships
MARKET POTENTIAL	4.22	3.78
INNOVATION	4.22	3.67
SCOPE AND REGIONAL INTEREST	4.22	3.89
CLIMATE, RISKS AND GHG EMISSIONS	3.33	3.22
DIGITALISATION	4.00	3.11
SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY	3.78	4.00
BUY A PRODUCT (market simulation)	80%	40%

After completing this phase under Task 3.2, the process moves to Task 3.3, the selected product will be launched and tested. It is planned an intensive workplan for the selected product, covering the following actions:

- Design and launch of the platform (pricing, structure, products, etc.)- booking agent and first questions
- Collaboration agreements between companies
- Intensive ad-hoc training and mentoring programmes for the development of skills at company level
- Accompanying procedures for certification acquisition - enterprise and tour guide level-
- Marketing plan and digital campaign (SEO, SEM, Ads)

Other activities related to Product 2 that can be assumed in parallel are related with:

- Prepare and sign collaboration agreements between companies from different regions wishing to cooperate in internships
- Intensive ad-hoc training and mentoring programme for the introduction of hydrophones
- Enabling relations with universities and granting programmes

7. ANEXXES

This section contains the agendas, participant numbers, signed attendance lists, agreements reached, model canvases for each idea, event photos, meeting minutes, and a link to all presentations used during the workshops.

PRESENTATIONS

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find all the presentations for both days.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find all the presentations for both days.

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find all the presentations for both days.

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find all the presentations.

MINUTES

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the minutes of the event.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the minutes of the event.

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the minutes of the event.

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the minutes of the event.

PHOTOS OF THE EVENT

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find pictures of the event.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find pictures of the event.

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find pictures of the event:

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find pictures of the event:

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AGENDAS

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

23 y 24 de septiembre de 2024

AGENDA / TALLER DE CO - CREACIÓN

Islas Canarias

www.twinnedbystars.eu

<p>Día 1. 23 de septiembre de 2024</p> <p>09.00h - 09.30h Bienvenida</p> <p>09.30h - 10.00h Presentación del proyecto, orden del día, objetivos, resultados esperados de la reunión <i>Xavier Martinez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN</i> <i>Frank A. Rodríguez, ASTROEDUCA</i></p> <p>10.00h - 10.30h El potencial de los cielos oscuros para mejorar tu oferta náutica <i>Frank A. Rodríguez, ASTROEDUCA</i></p> <p>10.30h - 11.00h P A U S A C A F É</p> <p>11.00h - 11.45h Ronda de presentaciones y presentación de la comunidad PYMES de TWINNEDbySTARS en su conjunto (Canarias, Azores, Madeira y Martinica) <i>Xavier Martinez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN</i> <i>Yen E. Lam González, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>11.45h - 12.05h Posibilidades tecnológicas en el sector náutico <i>Izzat Sabbagh Rodríguez, XREALITY FACTORY</i></p> <p>12.05h - 12.20h Pesca turismo, Turismo acuícola y Turismo pesquero y marinerío <i>Francisco García Lascruain, CAPITÁN MARÍTIMO DE LAS PALMAS</i></p> <p>12.20h - 12.30h Homogeneización y fomento de la certificación <i>Adelina de la Jara, CLUSTER MARÍTIMO DE CANARIAS</i></p> <p>12.30h - 13.00h Fase de ideación <i>Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>13.00h - 15.30h A L M U E R Z O</p> <p>15.30h - 16.30h Mesas temáticas: Canary Islands – Madeira – Azores – Martinica <i>Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>16.30h - 17.30h Presentaciones de las mesas, recapitulación y selección de ACUERDOS y RESPONSABILIDADES CONJUNTAS <i>Xavier Martinez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>20.00h Actividad de Teambuilding</p>	<p>Día 2. 24 de septiembre de 2024</p> <p>09.30h - 10.00h Estrategias ambientales para hacer tu negocio más circular <i>Mayte Tames Espinosa, ELITTORAL</i></p> <p>10.00h - 10.30h Presentación de la encuesta individual online de autoevaluación <i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>10.30h - 11.00h P A U S A C A F É</p> <p>11.00h - 11.30h Discusión sobre los resultados de la encuesta individual en línea para la autoevaluación. Momento de reflexión <i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>11.30h - 12.30h Identificación de necesidades y co-diseño de los cursos de formación <i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p>
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EDIFICIO FUNDACIÓN PUERTO LAS PALMAS

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Figure 12. Canary Islands' agenda.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD - 24TH OCTOBER 2024

23 e 24 de outubro de 2024

AGENDA / WORKSHOP DE CO-CRIAÇÃO

Madeira

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<p>DIA 1. QUARTA-FEIRA, 23 DE OUTUBRO DE 2024</p> <p>09.00h - 09.15h Boas-vindas (welcome) <i>Assis Correia, ACIF-CCIM</i></p> <p>09.15h - 09.30h Apresentação do projecto, agenda, objectivos e resultados esperados <i>Isabel Vieira, ACIF-CCIM</i></p> <p>09.30h - 10.30h Ronda de melhores práticas. Abordagem Ecológica à Observação de Golfinhos e Baleias <i>Declan Hoble, Magic Dolphin</i> VMT Madeira: Uma Stakeholder da Sustentabilidade <i>Sara Jardim, VMT Madeira</i> On-board education, science and interpretation <i>Miguel Danilo Morales Vargas, Biocean</i> Atividades e objetivos da Associação de Astronomia da Madeira <i>Duarte Oliveira, Astroturismo</i></p> <p>10.30h - 11.00h P A U S A P A R A C A F É</p> <p>11.00h - 11.30h Ronda de apresentações pelos participantes <i>Xavier Martinez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i> Apresentação da Comunidade de PME TWINNEDbySTARS: Açores, Ilhas Canárias, Madeira e Martinica <i>Teresa Gubern, FPCT-ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>11.30h - 12.00h Fase de ideação <i>Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>12.00h - 13.00h Mesas temáticas I. Objectivar Ideias <i>Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>13.00h - 14.00h P A U S A P A R A A L M O Ç O</p> <p>14.00h - 15.00h Mesas temáticas II. Preparação do Business Model Canvas <i>Gerard Martínez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>15.00h - 16.00h Apresentação dos resultados das mesas temáticas. Resumo e seleção de acordos e responsabilidades conjuntas <i>Xavier Martinez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>18.00h Atividade de teambuilding</p>	<p>DIA 2. QUINTA FEIRA, 24 DE OUTUBRO DE 2024</p> <p>09.00h - 9.30h Homogeneização empresarial e promoção de certificados <i>Mónica Quesada, CLUSTER MARÍTIMO DE CANARIAS (remote)</i></p> <p>09.30h - 10.00h Apresentação do questionário individual online para auto-avaliação <i>Teresa Gubern, FPCT-ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>10.00h - 11.00h Discussão dos resultados do questionário individual para auto-avaliação. Momento de reflexão & Identificação de necessidades. Co-desenho dos cursos de formação <i>Teresa Gubern, FPCT-ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>11.00h - 11.30h P A U S A P A R A C A F É</p>
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ACIF-CCIM
Rua dos Aranhas, 26 - Funchal

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Figure 13. Madeira's agenda.

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3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

13 et 14 novembre 2024

AGENDA / ATELIER DE CO-CRÉATION

Martinique

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JOUR 1. MERCREDI 13 NOVEMBRE 2024

13th Nov., Code: 657591

JOUR 2. JEUDI 14 NOVEMBRE 2024

<p>08.30h – 09.00h 11.30 - 12.00 Açores 12.30 – 13 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Mots de bienvenue <i>Patricia Telle, CTM MARTINICA</i></p> <p>09.00h – 09.30h 12.00 - 12.30 Açores 13.00 - 13.30 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Présentation du projet, de l'ordre du jour, des objectifs et des résultats attendus de la réunion <i>Marie Claude Derne, CTM MARTINICA</i></p> <p>09.30h – 09.45h 12.30 - 12.45 Açores 13.30 – 13.45 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Proposition de produit: ecoRoute sister project. <i>Jean Sébastien Guilbert, Université des Antilles</i></p> <p>09.45h – 10.15h 12.45 - 13.15 Açores 13.45 – 14.15 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Bonnes pratiques: Le cargo à voile, une solution innovante, écologique, économique et certifiée <i>Daniel EGALARD, SEAFRET</i></p> <p>10.15h – 10.45h 13.15 - 13.45 Açores 14.15 – 14.45 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>P A U S E</p> <p>10.45h – 11.00h 13.45 - 14.00 Açores 14.45 – 15.00 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Opportunités de vedettariat pour les entreprises de tourisme nautique. Proposition de produit: Atlantic Starlight charter experience <i>Lydia Cabau, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p> <p>11.00h – 11.15h 14.00 - 14.15 Açores 15.00 – 15.15 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Proposition de produit: Programme de stage au bord et hydrophones <i>Misael Morales Vargas, BIOSEAN</i></p> <p>11.15h – 11.30h 14.15 - 14.30 Açores 15.15 – 15.30 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Gestion environnementale d'une marina <i>Simon JEAN-JOSEPH, Le PORT du MARIN, Pavillon bleu</i></p> <p>11.30h – 12.30h 14.30 - 15.30 Açores 15.30 – 16.30 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Présentation des participants et entreprises de Martinique <i>Lydia Cabau, NAUTIC OCEAN</i></p>	<p>09.00h – 09.30h 12.00 - 12.30 Açores 13.00 – 13.30 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Présentation des outils d'homogénéisation des entreprises et des certifications <i>Mónica Quesada, CLUSTER MARÍTIMO DE CANARIAS (en distanciel)</i></p> <p>09.30h – 09.45h 12.30 - 12.45 Açores 13.30 – 13.45 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Transformation des produits de la mer <i>Clément DROMER, TI-FUMES DE CLEMENT</i></p> <p>09.45h – 10.00h 12.45 - 13.00 Açores 13.45 – 14.00 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Bonnes pratiques: Le transport maritime durable dans la Caraïbe <i>Gilles MARSAL, CANOPEE BLEUE</i></p> <p>10.00h – 10.15h 13.00 - 13.15 Açores 14.00 – 14.15 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>De nouvelles pratiques éco-touristiques pour les excursions en mer <i>Delice Nouel, Voile Nature</i></p> <p>10.15h – 10.45h 13.15 - 13.45 Açores 14.15 – 14.45 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Présentation du questionnaire individuel en ligne pour l'auto-évaluation <i>Yen Lam González, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p> <p>10.45h – 11.15h 13.45 - 14.15 Açores 14.45 – 15.15 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>P A U S E - C A F É</p> <p>11.15h – 12.00h 14.15 - 15.00 Açores 15.15 – 16 Canarias/Mad</p> <p>Discussion des résultats du questionnaire individuel, temps de réflexion + Identification des besoins et co-conception des formations <i>Yen Lam González, ULPGC-TIDES</i></p>
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JOUR 3. VENDREDI 15 NOVEMBRE 2024

15th Nov., Code: 657591

JOUR 4. SAMEDI 16 NOVEMBRE 2024

JOUR 5. DIMANCHE 17 NOVEMBRE 2024

JOUR 6. LUNDI 18 NOVEMBRE 2024

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Figure 14. Martinique's agenda.

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4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

**THURSDAY 28th - WP3 CO-CREATION WORKSHOP
WITH ENTERPRISES**

[Azores Marine Observatory \(OMA\)](#)
Fábrica da Baleia de Porto Pim, Monte da Guia
9900-000 Horta
 Hybrid Event – Connection link [here](#)

08:30 – 09:00	PARTICIPANTS' ARRIVAL AND REGISTRATION
09:00 – 09:15	Opening by Hosting Partner (<i>DRPM – Azores</i>)
09:15 – 09:45	Project presentation (<i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i>) Agenda, Objectives, Expected Results of the meeting (<i>Xavier Martínez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN</i>)
09:45 – 10:45	Conference Pills on Good Practices and product proposition Starlight charter opportunities for marine tourism companies. Product proposal: Atlantic Starlight charter experience (<i>Xavier Martínez Sirvent, NAUTIC OCEAN</i>) Ecological diving. Electrosolar diving support boat. (<i>Gilles Marsal, CANOPEE BLEUE</i>) Entrepreneurship in the Blue Economy Advantages of an ecosystem model (<i>Ana Rodrigues, ADFMA - Associação para o Desenvolvimento e Formação do Mar dos Açores</i>) Product proposal: On-board Internship programme (<i>Gisela Dionísio, Naturalist</i>) Product proposal: Whale watching acoustic experience. (<i>Misael Morales Vargas, Biosean</i>)
10:45 – 11:15	Round of presentations by participants (<i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i>) Presentation of the TWINNEDbySTARS SME Community as a whole within Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, and Martinique (<i>Teresa Gubern, ULPGC-FCPCT</i>)
11:15 – 11:45	COFFEE BREAK
11:45 – 12:15	Ideation phase (<i>Gerard Martinez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i>)
12:15 – 13:15	Thematic Tables (CANVAS models) (<i>Gerard Martinez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i>)
13:15 – 14:15	Tables' Presentations, Wrap-Up, and Selection of Agreements and Joint Responsibilities (<i>Gerard Martinez, NAUTIC OCEAN</i>)
14:15 – 15:15	LUNCH BREAK
15:15 – 15:30	Business homogenisation and promotion of certificates (<i>Mónica Quesada, CMC</i>)
15:30 – 16:30	Circularity, technical and capacity needs. Individual online survey for self-assessment as a moment of reflection. (<i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i>)
16:30 – 17:30	Identification of needs and co-design of the training courses (<i>Matias M. González Hernández, ULPGC-TIDES</i>)
17:30 – 19:00	SOCIAL PROGRAMME + COCKTAIL

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Figure 15. Azores' agenda.

LIST OF REGISTRES

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the **35** participants who signed for the event.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the **22** participants who signed for the event.

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the **39** participants who signed for the event.

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the **34** participants who signed for the event.

LIST OF FINAL ATTENDANTS / PARTICIPANTS

Ultimately, some individuals attended the event without signing in, while others signed up but did not participate. Below are the confirmed final attendance figures, verified through the signature list, photographs, and the ULPGC team’s registration records in Excel.

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

Table 3. Attendance per category for Canary Islands.

Total	32
SMEs	9
Civil, NGOs	1
Other stakeholders (speakers, governmental bodies, etc).	3
Partners	17

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

Table 4. Attendance per category for Madeira.

Total	21
SMEs	10
Civil, NGOs	2
Other stakeholders (speakers, governmental bodies, etc).	1
Partners	8

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

Table 5. Attendance per category for Martinique.

Total	40
SMEs	16
Civil, NGOs	2
Other stakeholders (speakers, governmental bodies, etc).	3
Partners	19

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

Table 6. Attendance per category for Azores.

Total	39
SMEs	16
Civil, NGOs	0
Other stakeholders (speakers, governmental bodies, etc).	3
Partners	17

SIGNATURE LIST

1ST WORKSHOP, CANARY ISLANDS, 23RD - 24TH SEPTEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the signature lists for both days.

2ND WORKSHOP, MADEIRA, 23RD – 24TH OCTOBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the signature lists for both days.

3RD WORKSHOP, MARTINIQUE, 13TH -14TH NOVEMBER 2024

As it was an online event, there was no signature list. According to zoom we had indeed **40** participants.

4TH WORKSHOP, AZORES, 28TH NOVEMBER 2024

[Here](#) you can find the signature list.

MODEL CANVASSES

In this section you can find the templates used for the workshops as well as the filled model canvasses per each product.

Business Model Canvas				
Socios clave	Actividades clave	Propuesta de valor	Relaciones con los clientes	Segmentos de clientes
Socios clave, proveedores, intermediarios, vendedores, gestores, etc.	Distribución, comunicación, compras, ventas, alquiler, procesos	¿Qué es novedoso, qué necesidad, deseo se cubre?	¿Con qué frecuencia interactuará con sus clientes?	¿Quiénes son los clientes? Describa a público objetivo
	Recursos clave		Canales de distribución y comunicaciones	
	¿Qué recursos se necesitan para echar a andar la idea y hacerla viable?		¿Cómo va a llegar a los clientes?	
Estructura de costes		Flujos de ingreso		
Tipologías y cuantificación de costes de lanzamiento y explotación		Precio final, productos similares, coste-beneficio		

Figure 16. Business Model Canvass template.

Canvas Medio Ambiente				
Suministros y subcontratación	Producción	Valor funcional	Final de la vida útil	Fase de uso
¿Cómo se asegura de que sus proveedores y actividades subcontratadas cumplen sus normas medioambientales y contribuyen a sus objetivos de sostenibilidad?	¿Qué medidas se aplican para minimizar los residuos, las emisiones y el consumo de energía en la producción?	¿Cómo integra su producto la sostenibilidad medioambiental con sus principales funciones y ventajas para los clientes?	¿Qué disposiciones se han tomado para el final de la vida útil del producto a fin de garantizar su eliminación o reciclado responsables?	¿Cómo fomenta el producto la sostenibilidad medioambiental durante su uso y qué apoyo se presta a los clientes para garantizarlo?
	Materiales		Distribución	
	¿Cómo se seleccionan los materiales a lo largo del ciclo de vida del producto?		¿Qué estrategias utiliza para minimizar el impacto ambiental de sus procesos de distribución y envasado?	
Impacto medioambiental		Beneficios medioambientales		
¿Cuáles son las principales repercusiones medioambientales de su producto y cómo las mide y mitiga?		¿Cuáles son los principales beneficios medioambientales de su producto y cómo se comunican a los clientes?		

Figure 17. Environmental Model Canvass template.

Figure 18. Social Model Canvass template.

AGREEMENTS

The following discussions and agreements were placed on each product:

Astronavigation product: **Atlantic Starlight Adventures** .

Table 7. Agreements Astronavigation table, 1st workshop, Canary Islands.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
KeepSailing, Dolphin-And-Whales, Bahiacat, Nauticocean (Gran Canaria), HappyHour (Madeira) should continue working on the upcoming workshops to address unanswered questions and finalize the Canvas (3 layers)	Done. 3 layers finished.
KeepSailing, Dolphin-And-Whales, Bahiacat, Nauticocean (Gran Canaria), HappyHour (Madeira) should define their team member to obtain the Starlight Monitor certification.	Pending.
ULPGC invites a representative from KeepSailing to Madeira/Azores workshops, covering travel expenses for one person, to continue working on the CANVAS.	They were invited, although finally they couldn't travel.
ULPGC will coordinate contact between Dolphin and Whales and French companies that have adopted	Contacts shared and Dolphin and Whales

electric motors for boats and will explore their participation in the workshop in Martinique.	participated in the Martiniquen workshop.
ULPGC will define which Spanish and Portuguese companies can attend the Martinique workshop.	Done.
ULPGC will integrate the results of the four workshops and activate the evaluation process to select the best business idea, which will be supported.	Done.
The Madeira/Martinique workshops should serve the members of this team to manage contacts for scheduling multi-day boat trips, especially between islands (commercial agreements should be generated).	Contacts made, boat trips pending.

Table 8. Agreements Astronavigation table, 2nd workshop, Madeira.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
Keep Sailing, Nautic Ocean, Happy Hour and Madeira Sunkiss Sailing to keep working on the development of the product	Done.
The Madeiran enterprises interested in incorporating stargazing activities will be invited to a training and mentoring activity covered by the project	It has been organized for WP2.
All enterprises will be invited to join the platform during the marketing campaign (product launch).	Pending.

Table 9. Agreements Astronavigation table, 3rd workshop, Martinique.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
The new interested enterprises will be incorporated to the working group.	Done.

Table 10. Agreements Astronavigation table, 4th workshop, Azores.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
One online meeting (before 15 December – Nautic Ocean) between the companies to finalise the Canvas sections	
The offerings/timing/prices of each company/island inside the platform is not defined (Nautic Ocean).	Pending.
The multi-destination experience (logistics) is not clear (Nautic Ocean).	Pending.

The topics of the commercial agreement should be defined (prices, commission, administrator, etc.) (Nautic Ocean).	Pending.
ULPGC will prepare an infographic summary of the product and the online voting system	Done.

Hydrophones, whale sounds and data. **Whale Whatching Acoustic Experience**

Table 11. Agreements Astronavigation table, 1st workshop, Canary Islands.

AGREEMENTS	STATUS
The ULPGC will invite the company Biosean as a speaker at the workshop in Madeira to exploit motivation and interest in the adoption of the technology.	Done, with great success and interest by the Portuguese companies.
The ULPGC will facilitate multiple meetings between Biosean and the companies to continue working on the business idea.	WhatsApp group created and various online meetings held.
Possible participation of Biosean in other workshops such as Martinique and Azores	Participated in all.
Sergio -Marina Funchal will contact a potential company to present its good practices in recycling at the Madeira ADRM workshop.	Contacted, although at the end it was not possible.
ADFMA evaluates to involve audio content in awareness raising activities or courses (prices and costs) to define a win-win strategy. Biosean and ADFMA can have online meetings facilitated by ULPGC.	Pending.
Biosean, and Marina do Funchal will use the next workshop in Madeira to answer unresolved questions and finalise the Canvas (3 layers).	Done. The two entities met. The initial idea was let as a training and the new Internship program idea was born.
Biosean and Canary On Board continue to work to complement the communication dimension of both products.	A podcast is being created by Canary On Board where there will be an episode on Acoustic experiences.

Table 12. Agreements Astronavigation table, 2nd workshop, Madeira.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
Mentoring on the use of hydrophones from Biosean.	Organised for WP2.
ULPGC will invite the Biosean enterprise as speaker to the workshop in Martinique to exploit motivating and interest from local enterprises	Done.

Table 13. Agreements Astronavigation table, 3rd workshop, Martinique.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
The newly interested enterprises will be incorporated to the working group and to the list for the training session.	Done

Table 14. Agreements Astronavigation table, 4th workshop, Azores.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
Companies agreed that this is not a product itself. Hydrophones use and sound data exploitation will be incorporated as part of the internship product.	Done.
A training/mentoring programme will be offered (free of charge) to all enterprises of the TbS community and their teams. ULPGC will certify the course	It will be organised for WP2 (see Figure 19, page 35).
The ULPGC contacted bilaterally to certain enterprises to define specific needs	Pending.

COURSE FACT SHEET (DRAFT)

Pre-Course Information

Course: How to use hydrophones for a whale watching acoustic experience		Trainer/s:
Training Location: 2 online masterclass + outings	Facilities Available:	No. Candidates:
Date of Course 1: Date of Course 2: Start Time:	Assessment/s planned:	

General aims:	
Specific learning outcomes for the course:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 40 min online hydrophones types, modernization, use, installation different boats, costs, maintenance, providers). - 40 min online ; species in each region, storytellings, environment and stressors, marine sound interpretation
Other learning outcomes:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real outings will be accompanied once enterprises acquire and install the hydrophones
Candidates are required to bring: No requirements. Each company decide the participants inside the teams. All the crew is welcome.*we can not financed the acquisition of hydrophones	

Figure 19. Draft of the training session on hydrophones planned "How to use hydrophones for a whale watching acoustic experience".

Education on board product. **Atlantic On-board internships**

Table 15. Agreements Astronavigation table, 2nd workshop, Madeira.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
Biosean, Naturalist and VMT should revise and finalise the business +2 canvas	Done.
Biosean, Naturalist and VMT should check what is exactly needed from TbS project to launch the regional cooperative action	Defined.
ULPGC will invite the Biosean enterprise as speaker to the workshop in Martinique to exploit motivating and interest from local enterprises	Done.
ULPGC will facilitate multiple encounters between Biosean and enterprises to keep working on the business idea until December 2024	Done, with online meetings and through a WhatsApp group.
ULPGC will try to engage other Canary Islands in the initiative emerging in Madeira	Sparked some interested but yet to have an official confirmation of an enterprise from another island to join the initiative.
Biosean, Naturalist and VMT should finalise the Canvas (3 layers).	Done.

Table 16. Agreements Astronavigation table, 3rd workshop, Martinique.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
The newly interested enterprises will be incorporated to the working group.	Done.

Table 17. Agreements Astronavigation table, 4th workshop, Azores.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
One online meeting (before 15 December –Biosean) between the companies to finalise the Canvas sections	Done
The offerings/timing/prices of each company/island in the platform is not defined (Biosean).	Pending.
The multi-destination experience (logistics) is not clear.	Pending.

The topics of the commercial agreement should be defined (prices, commission, administrator, etc.).	Pending.
ULPGC will prepare an infographic summary of the product and the online voting system	Done.

Storytelling: themed routes. **Historical and cultural heritage-focused thematic journeys, including star gazing and regional stories.**

Table 18. Agreements Astronavigation table, 2nd workshop, Madeira.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
The leading Company should define the needs and support required from TbS project	Not done so this idea was DISREGARDED.
Revise and finalise the Canvas.	Not done so this idea was DISREGARDED.

Table 19. Agreements Astronavigation table, 3rd workshop, Martinique.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
The newly interested enterprises will be incorporated to the working group with the hope of the group to finish the canvass	Done.

Citizen Science, product 3. **Citizen Science and Slow Tourism.**

Table 20. Agreements Astronavigation table, 4th workshop, Azores.

AGREEMENT	STATUS
One online meeting (before 15 December –ADFMA) between the companies to finalise the Canvas sections	Not done so this idea was DISREGARDED.
The offerings/timing/prices of each company/island in the platform is not defined (ADFMA).	
The multi-destination experience (logistics) is not clear (OMA please check).	
The topics of the commercial agreement should be defined (prices, commission, administrator, etc.)	
ULPGC prepare an infographic summary of the product	Unable to do.

PARALLEL ACTIVITIES

WP2 Training Needs

After all the workshops, the following were the main needs that arose from the enterprises:

- Electric motors – tailored recommendations and expert advice
- Use of the hydrophone and its application to storytelling and on-board education. Different uses for gamification, sensibilisation and increase tourist satisfaction
- Training in SEO and web optimisation to reduce dependency on tour operators.
 - Meta, Google Ads
 - SEM, SEO
- AI based Automatisation (CRM, Email marketing, social media campaigns).
- Astro-navigation training programme
 - Training course (60 hrs-optional)
 - Accompanying and mentoring in real outings
 - Starlight monitor certification

Activities in Azores:

- Escola do Mar: site visit was organized with ADFMA to showcase the enterprises that had to travel earlier to the Azores due to limited flight options. This visit highlighted the progress of the Escola do Mar's initiatives in training for maritime professions.
- Review Meeting: A consortium meeting was held on the day prior to the co-creation workshop to assess the project's progress and plan further steps for ongoing initiatives, ensuring alignment with the broader project objectives.
- Seafret Looking for a Boat: As the wait in Horta was long due to limited travel options back to Martinique, Seafret used this time to search for a boat that fit their interest in starting to transport small cargo volumes while also integrating into tourism activities.

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